

Quantum Calculus ($q = e^h$) and the Radioactive Decay Law

Shawn K. Eastmond
Independent Researcher, Bridgetown, Barbados
shawn.eastmond@gmail.com

March 29, 2020

Abstract

The radioactive decay law was first formulated by Ernest Rutherford and Frederick Soddy in 1902. As a well-known law, one of its primary applications is to determine the date of ancient specimens. The process is known as radiocarbon dating and is subjected to the known properties of radioactive nuclei. In this paper, we implement quantum calculus ($q = e^h$) to express the solution of the radioactive decay equation as a q -exponential function. Also, we determine the q -analog of its Half-life. Furthermore, the factor-label method was applied to our analysis to show that the correct units remained intact under the application of quantum calculus. In conclusion, we showed that a variation of the q -parameter was akin to the production of a new isotope $\forall q \in (0, 1)$.

Keywords: q -calculus, radioactive decay, half-life, factor-label method

1 Introduction

1.1 Classical decay

A known solution to the radioactive decay equation can be yielded from an elementary technique in ordinary differential equations known as the separation of variables[1]. Of course, this is not the only method to solve such

an equation. Another method which ensures an identical solution to the previous equation is the power series method. However, if we let the initial conditions of our system be as follows: at time $t = 0$, $N(t) = N_o = a_o$. Then the solution by the power series method is determined by substituting Eq.(2) in Eq.(1) to give Eq.(3),

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -\lambda N \quad (1)$$

$$N(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} a_n t^n \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} (n+1)a_{n+1}t^n + \lambda \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} a_n t^n = 0. \quad (3)$$

The terms a_n and a_{n+1} are related and hence the power series[6] solution is attained by substituting a_n in Eq.(2) where,

$$a_n = \frac{(-1)^n (\lambda)^n}{n!} a_0 \quad (4)$$

and

$$N(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} \frac{(-1t)^n (\lambda)^n}{n!} a_0. \quad (5)$$

A quicker and perhaps more straightforward method to find the solution to Eq.(1) is by seperating variables[11]. The terms N_0 , $N(t)$, λ , and t are: (i) the number of nuclei at $t = 0$, (ii) the number of nuclei at $t > 0$, (iii) the radioactive decay constant, and (iv) the time t , respectively. Furthermore, if we integrate Eq.(1) using the method of seperation of variables, we get

$$\int_{N_0}^{N(t)} \frac{dN}{N} = -\lambda \int_0^t dt \quad (6)$$

$$N = N_o \exp(-\lambda t). \quad (7)$$

1.2 Quantum calculus ($q = e^h$)

Quantum calculus[3] or sometimes called q -calculus is calculus done without limits. The term h in $q = e^h$ is used as a reminder of the planckian constant,

while the term q stands for "quantum". In the limit $h \rightarrow 0$, $q \rightarrow 1$ and the classical form of calculus is recovered[10]. Furthermore, another important point in q -calculus which will be discussed later in more detail, is the derivative and its q -analog (it is important to point out that currently no q -analog for the generalized chain rule exist [10]). Given these points, the downward arrow between Eqs.(8) and (9) illustrates the removal of the limit, which is replaced by the number one and hence,

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{qx - x} \quad (8)$$

↓

$$\frac{df}{dx} = \left\{ 1 \right\} \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{qx - x}. \quad (9)$$

2 q -Basics

2.1 The q -integer

Given that $0 < q < 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the q -integer is defined by:

$$[n]_q = \begin{cases} \frac{1-q^n}{1-q}, & \text{if } q \neq 1, \\ n, & \text{if } q = 1, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

for $q \in \mathbb{R}[4]$.

2.2 The q -factorial

Let $0 < q < 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then the q -factorial[4] is defined as follows from 2.1:

$$[n]_q! = \begin{cases} [n]_q [n-1]_q \dots [1]_q, & n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \\ 1, & n = 0. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

2.3 The q -logarithmic function

Let q be a real parameter defined on the open interval $(0, 1)$ [17], then the q -logarithmic function [4] is defined by:

$$\ln_q(x) = \begin{cases} \ln(x), & x > 0, \text{ and } q = 1, \\ \frac{x^{1-q}-1}{1-q}, & x > 0, \text{ and } q \neq 1, \\ \text{undefined}, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, it is now convenient to show that in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$, $\ln_q(x)$ goes to:

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{\ln_q(x)\} = (-1) \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} (x^{1-q}) \quad (13)$$

and

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{\ln_q(x)\} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{du} (e^{u \cdot \ln(x)}) = \ln(x), \quad (14)$$

where we have made the substitution ($u = 1 - q$), in Eq.(14).

2.4 The q -derivative

Let $f(x)$ be a function that is differentiable and hence continuous; then its q -derivative [5] is defined by:

$$(D_q f)(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(qx)}{(1-q)x}, \quad (15)$$

for $x \neq 0$. In the limit that $q \rightarrow 1$,

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (D_q f)(x) = \frac{df(x)}{dx}, \quad (16)$$

and we recover the classical form of the derivative. Furthermore, following from the definition of the q -derivative[12], for constants α and β there exist a linear relationship such that:

$$D_q \{\alpha f(x) + \beta g(x)\} = \alpha D_q \{f(x)\} + \beta D_q \{g(x)\}. \quad (17)$$

Henceforth, using Eqs. (15) and (17), we may write the product formula for $x \neq 0$ as:

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\{f(x)g(x)\} &= \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(x)g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(qx)g(qx) - f(qx)g(x) + f(qx)g(x) - f(x)g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(qx)(g(qx) - g(x))}{(q-1)x} + \frac{(f(qx) - f(x))g(x)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= f(qx)D_qg(x) + D_qf(x)g(x).
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

In like manner, the quotient rule and a non-generalized example that leads to a limited definition of the chain rule-no generalized chain rule currently exist-are given by[10],

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\left\{\frac{f(x)}{g(x)}\right\} &= \frac{1}{(q-1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(qx)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} + \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)} - \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right\} \\
&= \frac{1}{g(qx)} \left\{ \frac{f(qx) - f(x)}{(q-1)x} \right\} + \frac{1}{(q-1)x} \left\{ \frac{f(x)g(x) - f(x)g(qx)}{g(qx)g(x)} \right\} \\
&= \frac{1}{g(qx)} D_qf(x) + \frac{f(x)}{g(qx)g(x)} \left\{ \frac{g(x) - g(qx)}{(q-1)x} \right\} \\
&= \frac{g(x)D_qf(x) - f(x)D_qg(x)}{g(qx)g(x)},
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and for an arbitrary function of the form $f(u(x)) = f(\alpha x^\beta)$ [10], where α and β are constants, we get the following equation for a special case of the chain rule[18],

$$\begin{aligned}
D_q\{f(u(x))\} &= D_q\{f(\alpha x^\beta)\} \\
&= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{(q-1)x} \\
&= \frac{f(\alpha q^\beta x^\beta) - f(\alpha x^\beta)}{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta} \times \frac{\alpha q^\beta x^\beta - \alpha x^\beta}{(q-1)x} \\
&= (D_{q^\beta}f)(u(x))D_q(u(x)).
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

2.5 The q -exponential function

The q -exponential function (with $q \in (0, 1)$) is defined by

$$e_q(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{[n]_q!}, \quad (21)$$

and it should be obvious that the classical exponential function e^x is recovered in the limit as q approaches one. The term in the denominator of Eq.(21), $[n]_q! = [1]_q[2]_q \dots [n]_q$ [7] is the only major difference between e^x and $e_q(x)$. Again, the fact that in the limiting case one can recover the classical form makes quantum calculus exceptionally beautiful. An exhibit of this beauty will be analyzed graphically by plotting the q -exponential function for different values of the q -parameter in our system[19] (the radioactive decay law).

3 The q -analog of the radioactive decay law

3.1 Quantum decay

The precursory definition of the q -exponential function in section (2.5) will enable us to write the solution for the radioactive decay equation by means of a suitable power series[2]. Notice that within the solution (Eq. 7), the radioactive decay constant λ is still present, as should be. Subsequently, this constant will be written in terms of its q -logarithmic function. It will then be shown graphically; if we let the q -parameter vary for values strictly between 0 and 1 [14], that the classical form is indeed recovered. We are able to achieve this by choosing a known isotope of oxygen (oxygen-22) with a corresponding half-life of 2.25 seconds. The choice of isotope is simply random, and there exist no reason why any other isotope with a known half-life would not serve the same purpose. The modified radioactive decay constant is the given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2.25s} \times \ln_q(2). \quad (22)$$

Let the power series for $N(t)$ be defined as was shown in Eq. (1), then

$$\frac{d_q N(t)}{d_q t} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n t^{n-1}. \quad (23)$$

Now given that $[0]_q = 0$, then

$$\frac{d_q N(t)}{d_q t} = [0]_q a_0 t^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n t^{n-1} \quad (24)$$

for $n \geq 1$. We then substitute Eq. (24) in (1) and this gives,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [n+1]_q a_{n+1} t^n + \lambda \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n t^n = 0. \quad (25)$$

The terms in Eq. (25), which are of the form a_n and a_{n+1} [8] are the coefficients of t^n , therefore we must equate them, which gives

$$a_{n+1} = -\frac{\lambda a_n}{[n+1]_q}. \quad (26)$$

The relationship between a_n and a_{n+1} allows us to generate the following terms:

$$a_1 = -\frac{\lambda a_0}{[1]_q}; \quad (27)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q}; \quad (28)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q}; \quad (29)$$

$$a_4 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q}; \quad (30)$$

$$a_5 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q[5]_q}; \quad (31)$$

$$a_6 = \frac{(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)(-\lambda)a_0}{[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q[4]_q[5]_q[6]_q}. \quad (32)$$

Given that,

$$[1]_q[2]_q[3]_q \dots [n]_q = [n]_q! \quad (33)$$

we may write a_n as,

$$a_n = \frac{(-1)^n \lambda^n a_0}{[n]_q!}. \quad (34)$$

We may now substitute a_n in Eq. (1), giving us

$$N(t) = N_0 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \lambda^n t^n}{[n]_q}, \quad (35)$$

and

$$N(t) = N_0 e_q^{-\lambda t} \quad (36)$$

which is the q -analog of the radioactive decay law.

3.2 The Half-life

The half-life ($t_{1/2}$) is the time it takes for the number of radioactive nuclei to decrease by half the original value [13]. In the classical form, it is written as

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{\lambda}, \quad (37)$$

where λ is the radioactive constant. The fact that $\ln_q(x)$ exist for $x > 0$ and $q \neq 1$, we may write $t_{1/2}$ as $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{\lambda}$, where $t_{(1/2)Oxy22}$ is the Half-Life of oxygen-22. It also allows us to move in the reverse direction to recover the classical form when $q \rightarrow 1$ as depicted below in Eq. (38),

$$t_{1/2} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{t_{(1/2)Oxy22}\} = -\lambda^{-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} \left\{ 2^{1-q} \right\} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}. \quad (38)$$

3.3 q -Exponential plots

The values we made use of for the q -exponential plots are related to the q -parameter $\forall q \in (0, 1)$ [15]. We selected q -values of: 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.7, and 0.9 respectively. These values were substituted in the q -logarithmic function and the numerical answer was divided by the half-life of oxygen-22 which is approximately 2.25 seconds. The final result is substituted into $e_q(-\lambda t)$ and plotted for values of $t = [0, 20]$, since $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{\lambda}$.

Figure 1: q -exponential plots for $q = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.7,$ and 0.9

The exponential plots in Fig. 1 exhibit a remarkably simple idea that is in alignment with the initial ansatz, as it relates to the radioactive decay law. As the q -parameter is varied, for example, for $q = 0.1$ (red) the exponential plot decays faster than the other plots. On the contrary, for $q = 0.9$ (black) the decay is slower. This suggests that as $q \rightarrow 0$ radioactive decay occurs faster. In words, faster decays correspond to more intense radiation[9], which is observed in our plots and is in agreement with the theoretical model. Finally, it is clear from our plots that a variation in the q -parameter (as $q \rightarrow 0$) has the effect of increasing the radioactive intensity. In contrast, as $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical form of the radioactive law is recovered.

4 Factor-label method

4.1 Unit-factor method

In this section, we applied the factor-label method (unit-factor method) to confirm that the units of our model remained invariant under variation of the q -parameter. The classical form of the radioactive law has the following units:

$$N(t) = N_0 \times [scalar] \quad (39)$$

$$(number - of - nuclei) = (number - of - nuclei) \times [scalar]. \quad (40)$$

A comparison of Eqs.(39) and (41) are in agreement with respect to the units, in the classical and quantum case, since

$$N(t) = N_o e_q(-\lambda t), \quad (41)$$

and

$$\lambda t = t \times \left\{ \frac{x^{1-q} - 1}{1 - q} \right\} / t_{1/2}, \quad (42)$$

which gives

$$S^{-1} \times S = 1 \times [scalar]. \quad (43)$$

Therefore, the units remain invariant $\forall q \in (0, 1)$. Now, in terms of the radioactive decay constant, the units for its q -analog also remain intact, since

$$\lambda = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{t_{(1/2)Oxy22}}, \quad (44)$$

with units of inverse seconds,

$$S^{-1} = \frac{1 \times [scalar]}{S} = S^{-1}. \quad (45)$$

5 Conclusion

5.1 Concluding remarks

We have shown in our analysis, that by using a suitable power series it is possible to write the q -analog for the radioactive decay law. In the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical form of the law was recovered. We extended our analysis to also show that the radioactive decay constant can be written in terms of its q -analog while the units remained invariant in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$. Furthermore, we generated some plots to strengthen our analysis for values of $q = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.7$ and 0.9 . After a simple but careful analysis of the plots in Fig. 1, we found that as $q \rightarrow 0$, the decay process occurred at a faster rate. In other words, the radioactive decay intensity increased.

On the contrary, as $q \rightarrow 1$ the plots approached the classical form of the law. For $t_{(1/2)Oxy22} = 2.25$ seconds and

$$\lambda = \left\{ \frac{x^{1-q} - 1}{1 - q} \right\} / t_{1/2}, \quad (46)$$

a variation in the q -parameter is akin to the production of new isotopes. This is synonymous with a known phenomenon in nuclear physics known as isotopic transmutation. Since each isotope has its own characteristic radioactive decay constant. Note, that while the half-life of the isotope (oxygen-22) remained constant $\ln_q(x)$ changed $\forall q \in (0, 1)$ [16].

References

- [1] W. T. Ang and Y. S. Park. *Ordinary Differential Equations*. Universal Publishers, 2008.
- [2] David Betounes. *Differential Equations: Theory and Applications*. Springer New York, 2010.
- [3] Martin Bohner and Thomas Hudson. Euler-type boundary value problems in quantum calculus. *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 9(JO7):19–23, 2007.
- [4] Thomas Ernst. A method for q -calculus. *Journal of Nonlinear Mathematical Physics*, 10(4):487–525, 2003.
- [5] Ahmed Fitouhi and Néji Bettaibi. Wavelet transforms in quantum calculus. *Journal of Nonlinear Mathematical Physics*, 13(4):492–506, 2006.
- [6] Ahmed Fitouhi and Kamel Brahim. Tauberian theorems in quantum calculus. *Journal of Nonlinear Mathematical Physics*, 14(3):324–340, 2007.
- [7] Ahmed Fitouhi, Kamel Brahim, and Néji Bettaibi. Asymptotic approximations in quantum calculus. *Journal of Nonlinear Mathematical Physics*, 12(4):586–606, 2005.
- [8] Shigeji Fujita and S. V. Godoy. *Mathematical Physics*. Wiley, 2010.
- [9] Klaus Hentschel, Friedel Weinert, and Daniel Greenberger. *Compendium of Quantum Physics*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009.
- [10] Victor Kac and Pokman Cheung. *Quantum Calculus*. Springer New York, 2012.

- [11] A.C. King, S Billingham, and S. R. Otto. *Differential Equations*. Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [12] A. Lavagno and G. Gervino. Quantum mechanics in q-deformed calculus. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 174(1), 2009.
- [13] B. R. Martin. *Nuclear and Particle Physics: An Introduction*. Wiley, 2011.
- [14] Tatjana Z. Mirković, Slobodan B. Tričković, and Miomir S. Stanković. Opial inequality in q-calculus. *Journal of Inequalities and Applications*, 1, 2018.
- [15] Akram Nemri and Belgacem Selmi. Sobolev type spaces in quantum calculus. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, 359(2):588–601, 2009.
- [16] Akram Nemri and Belgacem Selmi. Calderón type formula in Quantum calculus. *Indagationes Mathematicae*, 24(3):491–504, 2013.
- [17] Krzysztof Piejko, Janusz Sokół, and Katarzyna Trąbka-Więclaw. On q-Calculus and Starlike Functions. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology, Transaction A: Science*, 43(6):2879–2883, 2019.
- [18] Jessada Tariboon and Sotiris K. Ntouyas. Quantum calculus on finite intervals and applications to impulsive difference equations. *Advances in Difference Equations*, 16:1–19, 2013.
- [19] Gokhan Yener and Ibrahim Emiroglu. A Q-analogue of the multiplicative calculus: Q-multiplicative calculus. *Discrete and Continuous Dynamical Systems - Series S*, 8(6):1435–1450, 2015.